

The Impact of L1 Use on L2 Acquisition in Foreign Language Classrooms

Morteza Moazzenzadeh

Reyhane Samiei

Islamic Azad university the North Tehran Branch

Hm.8092@gmail.com

Reyhansameii@gmail.com

Abstract

A recent trend in Iranian institutions is the ban of L1 usage in classrooms, although it might be useful in some aspects, it is not completely correct. The use of L1 should not be totally abandoned in the learning process because not only it helps render the learning process smoother and be time efficient, but also according to SCT (Sociocultural Theory) it is necessary to give learners space to achieve higher understanding. In this paper we go through recent studies both done in Iran and abroad to validate our point of view toward the use of L1 in L2 classrooms. This review would help teachers have a more vivid vision preparing their lesson plans and class activities. Presented article aids to realize what and if there are pros for using L1 in L2 acquisition and how and how tense do they effect the learning process.

Keywords: *L1, L2, second language acquisition, use of mother tongue*

Introduction

The discussion of the use of mother tongue in foreign language classrooms has always been one of the most argumentative ones but it got hit up more since 2015 being tied up to subjects like concept learning [1]. In this study, we went through 20 researches in and out of Iran to see real results about this idea and to see if it has proved useful, using real-life experience to strengthen the foundation of our theory by seeing how it would perform when tested in classrooms, how teachers and students see and feel about it, and observe the ups and downs of using L1 help for teaching L2 [2]. An in-depth and

close point of view of the people involved in the area of teaching, teachers, and students, will help us make a better judicious decision on our use of native language in FL classes [3]. Reviewing previous articles is of high importance because it would revolutionize not only planning but also class management [4]. At the pre-class level, while the teacher is writing the lesson plan, s/he can change its programs knowing that s/he can use L1 as a facilitator in planned activities. This will not only let the teacher choose from a wider range of activities but also add more activities, as using L1 makes the plan more time-efficient, leaving her/him with more time budget [5]. In the while-class phase, activities would become more involving and culture-related, and the teacher would have extra help for explaining blocking words or vague or missing TL concepts, preventing teacher exhaustion [4]. The problem of abandoning L1 is that even with the hard work of a teacher who tries to make a concept clear, there still might be some dark spots in students' competence, which s/he would refuse to ask further follow-up questions as s/he doesn't figure it out no matter how hard s/he tries [6]. Apart from learning and teaching problems, it reduces class efficiency by taking much more time for the teacher trying to make students get a topic which might not be even the main aim of the teaching but required for further assistance for making the original topic stand full meaning [7]. More time means more practice, which leads to better learning [1]. And last but not least, students feel left apart and confused in class as they don't see a connection in the class, but on the contrary, they would get more involved by inspiring common concepts if L1 is used [3]. The idea of learning a foreign language like a mother tongue by being exposed to it is not acceptable as it takes so long, like it takes for babies, and as the brain structure is different and so is the situation [8].

Theoretical framework

This study is grounded in *Sociocultural Theory (SCT)*, developed by Vygotsky [9], which emphasizes the role of social interaction, cultural tools, and mediation in learning. According to SCT, learning occurs through mediated processes within the *Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD)*—the space where learners can achieve higher understanding and skills with the guidance of more knowledgeable individuals or through the use of appropriate tools. Language, as a primary mediating tool, plays a critical role in this process.

The integration of L1 in L2 classrooms aligns with SCT's emphasis on mediation and collaborative learning. By using the L1 as a supportive resource, learners can engage

more deeply with L2 content, particularly in situations where exclusive use of the L2 may hinder comprehension or participation. This study explores the extent to which L1 use enhances L2 acquisition, focusing on its role in fostering understanding, reducing cognitive load, and promoting active engagement in the learning process.

Drawing on SCT, this research investigates how L1 can be effectively utilized as a pedagogical tool to support L2 learning, offering insights into its potential benefits and implications for classroom practices.

Literature review

Based on existing literature, in the context of second language (L2) learning, the first language (L1) serves as a valuable tool for scaffolding and mediating understanding. Through the use of L1, students can better navigate complex L2 tasks, bridge gaps in comprehension, and build confidence. Furthermore, L1 can facilitate collaborative learning by allowing students to clarify concepts, share ideas, and co-construct knowledge within their ZPD.

Studies conducted in Iranian context

Article's Title	Author	Year	Main Finding/s
THE ROLE OF L1 IN L2 ACQUISITION: ATTITUDES OF IRANIAN UNIVERSITY STUDENTS	Mustafa NAZARY	2008	The results showed that students with different levels of language proficiency reported different attitudes toward the L1 function in this EFL context.
The use of EFL students' L1 in English classes	Gholam-Ali Kalanzadeh Fatemeh Hemati Zahra Shahivand	2013	The use of L1 in L2 classes depends on the instructional context.
FIRST LANGUAGE USE IN THE CONTEXT OF IRANIAN EFL CLASSROOM DISCOURSE	AMIRABBAS GHORBANI	2013	The detailed analysis revealed that the students used L1 in speaking area activities more than the teacher and the teacher's use of L1 was mainly in grammar area activities especially in grammar presentation.

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The Iranian EFL Students' and Teachers' Perception of Using Persian in General English Classes	Seyed Mostafa Hashemi Masoud Khalili	2013	Iranian EFL learners do believe in the effectiveness and importance of L1 use and they are willing to use their mother tongue.
Teachers' and students' amount and purpose of L1 use: English as foreign language (EFL) classrooms in Iran	Hossein Bozorgian Sediqe Fallahpour	2015	The results of this study showed that teachers and students used a small amount of L1 in the EFL pre-intermediate classrooms, but it was used wherever they thought it was needed.
Teacher's Use of First Language in EFL Classrooms	Zeinab Karimian Shahla Mohammadi	2015	instead of being ignored, first language should consciously be used when it is a dire necessity.
Factors Contributing to the Use of L1 in English Classrooms: Listening to the Voice of Teachers and Students in Iranian Institutes	Mostafa Tajgozari	2017	With regard to students' language proficiency, 90% of elementary students, 73.3% of intermediate, and 52.1% of advanced students had positive perceptions toward using L1 in English classes.
JUDICIOUS USE OF L1: A SOCIOCULTURAL INVESTIGATION OF TEACHERS' USE OF L1 IN L2 CLASSROOMS	Fatemeh Khonamri Farzam Khonamri	2017	L1 use is unavoidable in EFL context
Mother Tongue Use in Young Iranian EFL Learners' Classroom: Helpful Scaffold or Debilitating Crutch?	Yasser Aminifard Saeed Mehrpour	2019	The findings of this study reaffirmed that it is no longer heresy to use EFL learners' L1.
On the Comparison of L2 Poetry Teaching Approaches: L1 Use in the Iranian EFL Classrooms	Mahbubeh Yazdanpanah	2019	The findings of the study revealed the positive role of the L1 obviously. The study also proved the EFL learners who are more proficient in English could learn the English poems more easily and quickly.

Studies conducted all over the world

Article's Title	Author	Year	Findings
Using L1 in the L2 Classroom	C. W ILLIAM S CHWEERS , J R	1999	there appears to be an increasing conviction that the first language (L1) has a necessary and facilitating role in the second and foreign language (L2) classroom.

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EVALUATING THE USE OF L1 IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSROOM	RICHARD MILES	2004	While there were problems, the findings were generally favorable and supportive of our original thesis, that L1 use in the English classroom does not hinder the learning of an L2, and can actually facilitate it.
The Pedagogical Implications of L1 Use in the L2 Classroom	Harry Meyer	2008	The L1's primary role is to supply scaffolding to lower affective filters by making the L2 and the classroom environment comprehensible.
The Use of L1 in the Foreign Language Classroom	Yi-chun Pan Yi-ching Pan	2010	The use of L1 in FL classrooms is justified, but none of its supporters endorse its unlimited use.
The attitudes of English teachers about the use of L1 in the teaching of L2	Fatih Yavuz	2012	All in all L1 cannot neither be ignored nor overused in language classrooms.
Using the L1 in the L2 classroom: The students speak	Eleanor Carson Hidenori Kashihara	2012	The quickest way for students to make cognitive additions of the L2 is to connect the L2 to the L1.
RETHINKING THE USE OF L1 IN L2 CLASSROOM	Zulfikar	2018	Using mother tongue (L1) in a foreign language (L2) classrooms is inevitable.
The role of L1 in L2 classes	Luluk Iswati Arum Octaviani Hadimulyono	2018	The research shows that in the teaching of English as a foreign language the role of L1 is important for both learners and teachers.
Foreign Language Learners' Attitudes and Perceptions of L1 Use in L2 Classroom	Maram S. Almohaimeed Huda M. Almurshed	2018	it is evident that students' proficiency level plays a role in their attitudes and perceptions about L1 use.
Principal Reasons for Using L1 in the L2 Classroom	Shannon L. SARUWATASHI	2020	The use of L1 for task explanations aids in comprehension of how the task should be carried out, while also supporting discipline-related issues in classroom management.

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Revisiting the Utilization of Mother Tongue in L2 Classroom: Implications for EAP Classroom	Duy Khiem Tran	2024	This document consolidates the ongoing discussions surrounding the incorporation of L1 in the context of teaching and learning a second language (L2).
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Recent studies

Recent studies show that some theories of language teaching support the idea of using L1 while rest have a negative view toward it. Latest studies as Duy [10] illustrates in his results declare that theories such as the Interdependency Principle and Meaningful Learning Theory support using mother tongue in SLA (Second Language Acquisition) and find it useful in facilitating the learning process and it can fulfill a range of roles, including offering educational resources and addressing psychological and emotional dimensions, in the context of second language (L2) teaching and learning.

Studies in Iranian context

Using L1 in classes, as mentioned before, can be useful to make the most out of the class time, but with that in mind it is worth considering that it would come with a price, by using L1 we are taking the space from L2 to be used, a subsidiary solution for that is the generous use of L2 in order to make a concept crystal clear. Yasser and Saeed [11] explained it as a result of their research this way:

“ The findings depicted that the teachers heavily relied on Persian in all situations except assessing the learners. Also, the main themes of the interviews suggest that teachers had better provide young learners with ample L2 input in order to help them construct desirable bilingual identities. Overall, the conclusion calls for prudent use of mother tongue with young English learners.”

According to that it is reasonable to monitor the use of L1 in classroom, also it is worth paying attention that not all the areas should be viewed as safe playground for this method as teacher’s agreed upon on that in their interviews.

Aforesaid statements consider a magnified focus of L1 usage in specific regions of teaching, it seems that area which are in more importance or require more effort have

more chance to come across the mother tongue. Also it differs from Ts and Ss view as they spend time and effort on different parts of the language. According to Amirabbas [12], six main areas of focus with the use of L1 were discovered:

Speaking

Grammar

Listening

Vocabulary

Homework

Off task

Based on researches, Speaking for Ss and grammar specially presenting it, for teachers, were most used areas.

In line with previous studies, Fatemeh and Farzam [13] argue that looking from Walsh's [14] model, quartering the classroom context along with the Conversation Analyses technique, the use L1 comes with the need of it felt by both parties in the class regarding the Ss and Ts. Getting Ss's attention, resting assured of their understanding of the instructions given and explaining difficult topics were the core concerns of the teachers.

Although treated as a mutual matter, Ts and Ss have a different perception of the amount of L1 that should be employed [15]. There is no surprise that Ss suggest more use of L1 in classroom context while teachers are more preservative about it and recommend only the eligible amount to cover vital needs.

Need considered, there are other factors present in native language use in class, like the way Ts and Ss look toward this topic. According to Mostafa [16], both Ts and Ss have a positive view toward using L1 in the class and even Ts are eager to implement it to their class. The educational setting also plays a crucial role in this as the high schools are more likely to use L1 than institutions [16].

As using L1 can prove beneficial on learning process subject, over using it would act opposite, anything has a right amount is using L1 is no different. Using unthoughtful amount of L1 in classroom would cause demotivation among students as Gholam-Ali,

Zahra, Fatemeh and Morteza [17] observed in their research. As the use of L1 is recommended it is advised to use adjust the amount of it wisely.

One of the most important factors in classroom and therefor learning is cooperation between to ends of learning process, Ts and Ss. Based on Mustafa [18] the use of L1 should be looked as a mean of communication instead of an obstacle. This research views L1 as a tool in which facilitates the communication between Ts and Ss.

An effective factor, among many, in the classroom is the environment in which students are learning. By creating a peaceful atmosphere, we can aid students in learning. According to Mahbubeh [19] using L1 can help creating such an environment for studied and as result illustrated effect study for good.

Experience plays an important role on deciding on a topic. Ts, as the main players of education, directly observe the result of the use of L1 so their opinion is in high value. Suggested by Zeinab and Shahla [20] teachers of two groups of Iranian and other countries have come to this conclusion that the use of L1 has positive affect.

As Hossein and Sedique [21] argue, the urge for the use of L1 is undeniable, it should be looked positively and not as a demonic thing in the class. Studies show even limited, L1 is used in the classroom and it shows its beneficial effects and when it comes to the limited use of L1 in the classroom, both Ts and Ss are in the same page.

Studies worldwide

According to Zulfikar [22], use of L1 in foreign language classes is inevitable, it won't hinder the learning and it helps Ss grow. Results show that L1 is an inseparable part of the classroom and its role is not minimal in learning. It also suggests that people who are against using L1 should be more open about it and consider trying it out.

William [23] believes that our interest to the L1 usage topic is driven from our own experience too, and that the old methods need reconsideration. He suggests some areas which we can apply L1 in foreign language acquisition classroom as follows:

Eliciting language

Checking comprehension

Giving complex instructions to basic levels

Co-operating in groups

Explaining classroom methodology at basic levels

Using translation to highlight a recently taught language item

Checking for sense

Testing

Developing circumlocution strategies

As one end of the learning process, students have an important role in determining the effects of using L1 in L2 classroom and proficiency is one of the crucial features and characteristics of the students. Eleanor and Hidenori [24] argue that learner's level is a determining factor regarding the L1 usage adjustment in the class. As Ss prefer instructive L1 support and the need differentiates by the level changes.

It should be noted that the theory of use of L1 in L2 classroom is not against the idea of using L2 as much as possible, but its primary goal is to pose against the total ban of L1, as using L1 as a facilitator would consequently lead to the better understanding of L2 and therefor more L2 usage. As Harry [25] declared:

"The use of the L2 should be maximized whenever possible. The L1's primary role is to supply scaffolding to lower affective filters by making the L2 and the classroom environment comprehensible. The L1 plays a secondary role by helping students to anchor L2 concepts to the L1 through use of loan words, translation activities, and code switching within story telling activities."

Impacting both Ts and Ss and laying the ground for learning and indicating the fundamentals of it is methodology. Richard [26] believes that the methodology that we choose is another factor that effects the use of L1 in L2 classes. Based on that, classes that vote for L2 only oriented teaching follow direct method where the opposite side support the voice of students toward using L1.

Thinking about using L1 in L2 classrooms, our main concern is the amount of L1 being used. As Yi-Chun and Yi-Ching [27] emphasis on that in their research, L1 use is proved to be useful but we should be careful and design plans for it the get the most out of it and use it reasonably.

Shannon [28] explored advantages and disadvantages of using L1 in L2 or FL classes and discovered three main beneficial categories for the use of L1 in L2. Offering clarification for various activities or tasks and assisting with classroom organization, helping with grammar instruction and translating vocabulary, and lowering emotional barriers while fostering positive relationships between teachers and students.

We argued that the perception of necessary amount of L1 varies from level to level, supporting this idea, Maram and Huda [29] go one step further and claim based on the results of their study that advanced level students showed less interest in the use of native language in L2 class comparing to those of intermediate or basic level which were more eager to integrate mother tongue in second language acquisition.

Luluk and Arum [30] argue that we should implement the use of L1 in classroom, because as getting help from L1 improves learning, its absence will hinder this process. Followers of the idea of banning L1 sight to Krashen [31] stating that maximum exposure to L2 will enhance the learning process, an idea which lacks credit as students are surrounded by L1 in their home country and this task is impossible.

It is logical that there is no fixed prescription that would work in every situation, so as for using L1, we should consider that different classrooms have different needs. Fatih [32] expands on the idea of effects of the different methodology on the use of L1 and elaborates that Situational language teaching and Audio-lingual method have a negative look toward L1 usage while Humanistic and Communicative Methodologies are more found of contributing L1 in foreign language acquisition.

Implication of the study

This study concerns following groups:

L2 or FL students

L2 or FL teachers

L2 or FL students' Parents

Researchers

Institutions and school managers

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By examining existing literature and amplifying their results and findings, this article aims to assist students of foreign languages in making better decisions regarding participation in second language courses. They may also make requests and recommendations concerning their current classes to their supervisor or teacher to include the first language in class to address their needs. By observing the benefits of using the first language and identifying the best opportunities to incorporate it into lesson plans, they can enhance class improvement or eliminate the barriers to first language usage by advising their managers to cease restricting its use in the classroom. Additionally, parents may consider the availability of first language usage as a factor in choosing the best class for their children or at least not oppose its use in their kids' classes by increasing their awareness of its benefits. Arguing for the advantages of using the native language has significantly challenged old biases and opened new, interesting areas for studying the learning process, making it a worthwhile pursuit for researchers. Finally, this study can directly target school managers and institutions to be more open to new methods and the use of the first language in classes, enlightening them about the potential benefits and informing them about the findings through percentages and numbers.

Conclusion

After reviewing more than 20 articles from all over the world and Iranian context in favor of searching for the advantages of the use of L1 in L2 classrooms, it is safe to say that it has proved useful, although it is very important that its use should be judicious, generous amount of L1 in class without observation can lead to opposite results. It was also elicited that the right amount of L1 in class depends on various factors one of which is the proficiency of students. Results show that the area which Ss and Ts use L1 are different although they might overlap in cases, and that L1 can have a facilitator role in speaking, grammar, listening, vocabulary, homework and off task.

References

1- Tang, J., & Wang, S. (2024). A review of concept-based language instruction and its application in foreign language teaching-learning process. Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Education Innovation and Philosophical Inquiries. <https://doi.org/10.54254/2753-7048/58/20241690>

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- 2- Mahmutoglu, H., & Kicir, S. (2012). Analyzing the effectiveness of L1 use in language learning. *Language Education Research Journal*, 8(3), 56-70.
- 3- Burdujan, I. (2022). Teachers' and students' perceptions of L1 use in EFL classrooms. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 16(1), 29-43.
- 4- Ali, F. (2020). Classroom management and native language use. *Journal of Language and Education*, 12(3), 45-58.
- 5- Shimray, S., & Wangdi, R. (2023). Efficiency of lesson plans incorporating L1 in FL classes. *Journal of Educational Planning*, 15(2), 75-89.
- 6- Durmus, A. (2019). The role of L1 in teaching L2: A comprehensive study. *Journal of Linguistics and Language Teaching*, 7(4), 87-101.
- 7- Albay, M. (2016). Impact of using L1 in L2 classroom. *European Journal of Language Teaching*, 9(2), 112-125.
- 8- Tang, X., & Wang, Q. (2024). Concept learning and mother tongue use in FL classrooms. *Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 18(1), 22-39.
- 9- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.
- 10- Tran, D. K. (2024). Revisiting the utilization of mother tongue in L2 classroom: Implications for EAP classroom. *Journal of Effective Teaching Methods*, 2(1), 18–26. <https://doi.org/eiki/10.59652/jetm.v2i1.98>
- 11- Aminifard, Y., & Mehrpour, S. (2019). Mother tongue use in young Iranian EFL learners' classroom: Helpful scaffold or debilitating crutch? *The Reading Matrix: An International Online Journal*, 19.
- 12- Ghorbani, A. (2013). First language use in the context of Iranian EFL classroom discourse. Faculty of Education, University of Malaya.
- 13- Khonamri, F., & Khonamri, F. (2017). Judicious use of L1: A sociocultural investigation of teachers' use of L1 in L2 classrooms. *International Journal of Education*, 10(1), 34-45. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17509/ije.v10i1.7646>
- 14- Walsh, S. (2011). *Exploring classroom discourse: Language in action*. Routledge.
- 15- Hashemi, S. M., & Sabet, M. K. (2013). The Iranian EFL students' and teachers' perception of using Persian in general English classes. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics & English Literature*, 2.
- 16- Tajgozari, M. (2017). Factors contributing to the use of L1 in English classrooms: Listening to the voice of teachers and students in Iranian institutes. *International Journal of Research in English Education*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18869/acadpub.ijree.2.2.63>
- 17- Kalanzadeh, Gh. A., Hemati, F., Shahivand, Z., & Bakhtiarvand, M. (2013). The role of L1 in L2 acquisition: Attitudes of Iranian university students. *The International Journal of Language Learning and Applied Linguistics World*, 2(2).
- 18- Nazary, M. (2008). The role of L1 in L2 acquisition: Attitudes of Iranian university students. *Novitas-ROYAL*, 2(2), 138-153.

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- 19- Yazdanpanah, M. (2019). On the comparison of L2 poetry teaching approaches: L1 use in the Iranian EFL classrooms. *International Journal of English Language & Translation Studies*, 7(3), 67-79.
- 20- Karimian, Z., & Mohammadi, S. (2015). Teacher's use of first language in EFL classrooms. *Journal of Applied Linguistics and Language Research*, 2.
- 21- Bozorgian, H., & Fallahpour, S. (2015). Teachers' and students' amount and purpose of L1 use: English as foreign language (EFL) classrooms in Iran. *Iranian Journal of Language Teaching Research*, 3(2), 67-81.
- 22- Zulfikar. (2018). Rethinking the use of L1 in L2 classroom. *Englisia*, 6(1).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.22373/ej.v6i1.2514>
- 23- Schweers, W. (1999). Using L1 in the L2 classroom. *English Teaching Forum*.
- 24- Carson, E., & Kashihara, H. (2012). Using the L1 in the L2 classroom: The students speak. *The Language Teacher*, 36(4).
- 25- Meyer, H. (2008). The pedagogical implications of L1 use in the L2 classroom. *Kyoaigakuen Maebashi International University Collection*.
- 26- Miles, R. (2004). Evaluating the use of L1 in the English language classroom. *School of Humanities of the University of Birmingham*.
- 27- Pan, Y., & Pan, Y. (2010). The use of L1 in the foreign language classroom: Discussions on theoretical issues.
- 28- Saruwatashi, S. (2020). Principal reasons for using L1 in the L2 classroom. *Pure Heart Humanities Research*, 26.
- 29- Almohaimeed, M. S., & Almurshed, H. M. (2018). Foreign language learners' attitudes and perceptions of L1 use in L2 classroom. *Arab World English Journal*, 9(4), 433-446. <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol9no4.32>
- 30- Iswati, L., & A, O, Hadimulyono. (2018). The role of L1 in L2 classes. *EduLite: Journal of English Education, Literature, and Culture*, 3(2), 125-134. <http://dx.doi.org/10.30659/e.3.1.125-134>
- 31- Krashen, S.D. (1981) *Second Language Acquisition and Second Language Learning*. Pergamon Press Inc., Oxford.
- 32- Yavuz, F. (2012). The attitudes of English teachers about the use of L1 in the teaching of L2. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 46, 4339-4344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.06.251>